

1 **Methods**

2 The material stock pattern indicators were derived from crowd-sourced data on infrastructures
3 (roads and railways)¹ as well as high-resolution land-cover data². The indicators refer to the
4 years 2015 (built-up land) and 2020 (roads and railroads). To reduce random fluctuations for
5 the energy and emission data as well as the conventional factors, we calculated averages for
6 as many years in the period 2015-2020 as were available in the statistical sources. Extensive
7 variables were represented by per-capita values to facilitate comparisons between different-
8 sized countries, following the convention to regard population as a scaling factor with an
9 elasticity of one in STIRPAT analyses³.

10

11 **Data used to derive spatial indicators**

12 The spatial indicators presented in this study rely on three spatially explicit datasets; (1) built-
13 up features and urban agglomerations, (2) main infrastructure features (road and railway) and
14 (3) an inhabited land area layer used for reference. All variables that express quantities as
15 fraction of a country's area, relate to inhabited land. We used the LC100 grid of the
16 Copernicus Global Land Cover Service⁴ to derive relevant land cover information. Choice of
17 input data and data quality checks are discussed in the SI; see also Extended Data Figure 1. In
18 contrast to other built-up land datasets⁵⁻⁷, the LC100 not only provides globally consistent
19 information on built-up areas, it also includes all other complementary land cover types at a
20 global scale. For data preparation, we vectorised the LC100 grid to allow further spatial
21 intersection procedures (e.g. to clip to national borders). The NOAA-DEM grid was used as a
22 global digital elevation model. We utilised the Geofabrik-download hub⁸ to obtain the entire
23 global OSM data. The GISCO archive from EUROSTAT⁹ provides the applied country
24 borders. Details on the data sources are given in Supplementary Table 1 (SI).

25

26 **Sources of energy and emission data as well as conventional factors**

27 Gross domestic product (GDP) in constant 2015 US\$ was sourced from UN Statistics
28 Division National Accounts¹⁰. Population data used to calculate population density (DENS)
29 and urban population rates (UPOP) were taken from official census data 2017 of the World
30 Bank^{11,12}. The World Bank database was also used to source data on pump prices for gasoline
31 (PGAS)¹³. Heating degree days (HDD) were calculated as a population-weighted average of
32 °C days above 18°C and sourced from the International Energy Agency (IEA) Weather for
33 Energy Tracker¹⁵. Territorial CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion and cement
34 production (CO₂) were sourced from the Global Carbon Project database^{16,17} and total final

35 energy consumption (TFC) from the IEA energy balances, which could only be accessed for
36 the latest year 2017¹⁸. Record date for the download of these indicators was 25th of March,
37 2021. We always used the latest available year for our cross-sectional analysis, but also
38 conducted robustness checks using arithmetic averages over the latest five years for all
39 indicators to exclude potential bias from outstanding annual values. Details on the data are
40 available in Supplementary Table 2 in the SI.

41

42 **Deriving the built-up land layer**

43 The built-up land vector (BL) for every country is one primary data product derived by the
44 vectorized LC100 grid. This standard BL layer comprises all national built-up features and
45 was used to derive the BL-related indicators shown in part (1) of Table 1 of the paper. To map
46 each country's urban agglomerations, and thereby distinguish urban from rural land
47 respectively infrastructures (see Extended Data Figures 2-4), we clustered features of the BL
48 vector layer using an empirical growing neighborhood approach: We started with the
49 country's largest BL feature and created convex hulls, which were buffered with the fifth of
50 the area-equal radius. We then identified intersecting BL features within this buffered hull and
51 created a new hull and buffer. These two steps were repeated as long as the BL area of all
52 intersecting features reached 33.3% of the area of the buffered hull (used to check the
53 intersections), and the BL area increased at least 0.5%, compared to the BL area of the
54 previous iteration. If these criteria were not given, the growing procedure terminated and the
55 collected BL features dissolved to one BL agglomeration. The algorithm subsequently went
56 on with the next-biggest BL feature, which had not been assigned to an already-created
57 agglomeration, again starting the above-described procedure with this next BL feature. The
58 whole process terminated when the next BL feature (to re-start the growing neighborhood
59 procedure again) represented less than 0.1% of the total BL area of the respective country.
60 The maps in Extended Data Figure 5 show the built-up (BL) land indicators. Fractions of land
61 areas refer to inhabited land.

62

63 **The infrastructure layers**

64 The preprocessed OSM database comprises globally consistent road (R) and railway vector
65 data (RW), but the availability of OSM data varies strongly between countries. While the
66 OSM data in countries of the global North (industrial or even postindustrial countries) also
67 include minor road and train track categories (e.g. cycleways, steps or private gauges), OSM
68 data in countries of the global South only comprise the main road and railway network. To

69 reduce this inconsistency, we excluded minor OSM classes in order to derive a more
70 comparable global database (Supplementary Table 3). The maps showing the road network
71 indicators are in Extended Data Figure 6. Fractions of area refer to inhabited land. The
72 railway indicators were derived from OSM in the same manner as those for roads and are
73 shown in Extended Data Figure 7. Railway types considered are defined in Supplementary
74 Table 4. Fractions refer to inhabited land. The planar extent of road and railway networks was
75 calculated using width data reported in Supplementary Table 5. The distinction between urban
76 and rural infrastructures was based on a spatial intersection of OSM road and railway data
77 with the BL features, which resulted in layers of urban and rural networks (example shown in
78 Extended Data Figure 4).

79

80 **Reference layer for inhabited land**

81 The definition of some material stock pattern indicators requires a reference area (A_{REF}). The
82 area of the total national territory (A_{NT}) may not be suitable, given that in some countries
83 (almost) the entire area is inhabitable, whereas other countries contain large tracts of land
84 unsuitable for human habitation and hence largely uninhabited. We therefore developed the
85 proxy layer “inhabited land” (IH) as a more suitable area reference (A_{IH}). In contrast to
86 existing similar datasets¹⁹, this IH mainly uses land cover information of the LC100 grid. This
87 guarantees thematic consistency in spatial intersections with BL data that were derived using
88 the same dataset. The IH includes not only area that is covered with settlements or
89 infrastructures, but also cropland areas and areas with ambiguous land cover that fall within a
90 zone of influence around existing built-up areas, which is approximated by a buffer that
91 depends on the area of a built-up land feature (Equation 1). The IH is based on the current
92 settlement and cropland extent, as well as the spatial distribution, density, and elevation
93 occurrence of built-up areas according to the LC100 grid.

94

95 To calculate IH, we first cut out high altitude regions from the country’s total territory. We
96 calculated the elevational distribution of BL features and excluded all areas above the area-
97 weighted 99th-percentile of BL-elevations. In a second step, we excluded the LC100 land
98 cover types “bare/sparse vegetation” (deserts and rocks), “moss & lichen”, “snow & ice” and
99 “permanent water bodies”. Thirdly, we spatially intersected the map resulting from the
100 previous two steps with a synthetic layer that represents the gapless inhabited land area. To
101 derive this layer, we applied an area-dependent buffer for all BL features. See equation 1 for

102 the dynamic BL buffer width (w_{BL}); $A_{BL\ feature}$ denotes the area of an exemplary built-up land
103 feature.

104

105 Equation 1:

$$w_{BL} = A_{BL\ feature}^{\frac{2}{3}}$$
$$\max\{w_{BL}: 100km\}$$

108

109 Finally, we added cropland areas (from LC100) and the original BL areas to re-include those
110 BL areas excluded by the elevation threshold. Please note that for spatial indicators that
111 depend on A_{REF} , the specific spatial pattern (shape) of IH is not relevant: we just use the
112 national total area of IH instead of the area of the national territory as reference value. The
113 potential usefulness of this IH layer for other research questions, in particular where its spatial
114 accuracy is of high importance, needs to be tested and is not in focus in this study.

115

116 **Definitions of spatial pattern indicators**

117 The spatial pattern indicators were derived from the built-up, road and railway layers. Details
118 on the definitions of the indicators (Table 1) are given in the SI in section 3, Supplementary
119 Tables 6-8.

120

121 **Pearson correlations**

122 The Pearson correlation is a measure of linear association between two variables. The
123 coefficient estimate can be obtained from bivariate data $\{(X_1, Y_1), \dots, (X_n, Y_n)\}$ as
124 $r_{XY} = S_{XY} / S_X S_Y$, where S_{XY} and S_i denote the sample covariance and standard deviation. The
125 correlation coefficient is between -1 and 1. Correlations equal to 1 (or -1) indicate a perfect
126 linear association, with data points lying exactly on a positive (negative) 45° line. A value
127 equal to zero indicates the absence of any linear association. The *squared* correlation
128 coefficient r_{xy}^2 is the coefficient of determination (R-squared) of the linear regression of
129 variable x on variable y; it measures the fraction of the variance explained by the regression
130 line.

131

132 **Semi-partial correlations**

133 Suppose that Y is determined by $\mathbf{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_k\}$. Then, the semi-partial correlation between
134 Y and X_i , controlled for the other predictors \mathbf{X}_{-i} , attempts to measure the correlation between
135 Y and X_i that would be observed if the effect of \mathbf{X}_{-i} would be removed from X_i but not from
136 Y . This means that the semi-partial regression measures the correlation between Y and the
137 part of X_i that is orthogonal to the other variables X_{-i} . It is calculated by constructing a new
138 variable X_i' that is ‘orthogonal’ (i.e. entirely uncorrelated) to all previously considered
139 variables (i.e. those ‘controlled for’).

140

141 The *squared* semi-partial correlation coefficient measures the fraction of the variance of the
142 dependent variable Y that is uniquely explained by X_i . Thus, it can also be interpreted as the
143 increase (decrease) in the model R-squared value that results from including (removing) X_i
144 from the set of predictors \mathbf{X} .

145

146 The semi-partial correlation is calculated by first fitting a linear regression of Y on \mathbf{X} and
147 computing the coefficient as

148

149 Equation 2:

150
$$r_{Y(X_i|\mathbf{X}_{-i})} = \text{sign}(t) \sqrt{\frac{t^2 (1 - R^2)}{n - k}},$$

151

152 where t is the t statistic of variable X_i in the previous regression, R^2 is the R-squared, k is
153 the number of independent variables plus the constant, and n is the sample size. Finally, the
154 significance level is given by $2 \Pr(t_{n-k} > |t|)$, where \Pr is the probability, t is as described
155 above and t_{n-k} follows a Student’s t distribution with $n - k$ degrees of freedom. Further details
156 on the correlation techniques used are available e.g. here²⁰.

157

158 **Lasso analysis**

159 The ‘least absolute shrinkage and selection operator’ (lasso) approach is used to select
160 variables for multivariate statistical models for predicting cross-country patterns of TFC and
161 CO_2 ^{21,22}. Lasso is a standard regularization technique for model selection and prediction that
162 overcomes disadvantages of other regularization techniques such as Ridge regression²³. It can

163 select a parsimonious set of variables from many potential covariates, even if covariates are
164 collinear. Lasso minimizes the sum of squared residuals, but unlike standard least-square fit
165 approaches it penalizes complexity in the objective function to derive the best parsimonious
166 model for any predefined value of λ , i.e. the factor penalizing model complexity. If λ is set to
167 zero, lasso delivers standard least squares estimates, which corresponds to a model with the
168 maximum complexity. In general, the larger the λ , the smaller the number of non-zero
169 coefficients.

170

171 Consider a linear specification $Y = B_0 + B_1X_1 + \dots + B_pX_p + \epsilon$, where variables have been
172 previously standardized to account for differences in scales. Lasso finds estimates for model
173 coefficients B_i keeping the model sparse by minimizing the following term:

174

$$175 \quad \frac{1}{2N} (y - XB)'(y - XB) + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |B_j|$$

176

177 The first part of the term is the in-sample squared error minimized by a classical least-squares
178 approach. Lasso also includes the absolute sum of coefficients in the objective function,
179 which penalizes complexity driving some of the estimated coefficients to zero.

180

181 The value of λ is typically chosen so that the estimated model satisfies a predetermined
182 condition. Several criteria can be employed, the most common of which is cross-validation.
183 Cross-validation selects the λ to minimize the out-of-sample prediction error. First, sample
184 observations are split into K random folds (validation sets). For each validation set, the model
185 is fitted using data from the other folds, and the out-of-sample deviance for the observations
186 in the validation set is computed (i.e., using data not employed for estimation). Finally, the
187 overall out-of-sample performance of the model in all the validation sets is assessed by the
188 ‘mean-square prediction error’ (MSPE), a statistical parameter in squared (log) units required
189 for model selection. Cross-validation selects the λ over a grid of possible values such that the
190 corresponding model has the minimum MSPE²¹. In Table 2, MSPE is transformed into r^2 , i.e.
191 goodness of fit within the sample of countries, and oSr^2 , i.e. the cross-validated out-of-sample
192 goodness of fit for the optimal models. If no variable is added or removed at λ^* , this is
193 reported in the left columns of Table 2 as ‘Unchanged’. Note that more variables could be
194 added beyond λ^* but would not further improve the out-of-sample prediction.

195

196 **Method references**

- 197 1. Geofabrik. *Open Street Map Data Extracts*. (Geofabrik Download Server, last download date 13.5.2020,
198 2020).
- 199 2. Buchhorn, M. *et al. Copernicus Global Land Service: Land Cover 100m: collection 2: epoch 2015: Globe*.
200 (Zenodo archive doi:10.5281/zenodo.3243509, 2019).
- 201 3. Liddle, B. Impact of population, age structure, and urbanization on carbon emissions/energy consumption:
202 evidence from macro-level, cross-country analyses. *Popul Environ* **35**, 286–304 (2014).
- 203 4. Marcel Buchhorn *et al.* Copernicus Global Land Service: Land Cover 100m: collection 2: epoch 2015: Globe.
204 (2019) doi:10.5281/zenodo.3243509.
- 205 5. Florczyk, A. J. *et al. GHSL Data Package 2019*. (Publication Office of the European Union, 2019).
- 206 6. Esch, T. *et al.* Where We Live—A Summary of the Achievements and Planned Evolution of the Global
207 Urban Footprint. *Remote Sensing* **10**, 895 (2018).
- 208 7. Gong, P. *et al.* Annual maps of global artificial impervious area (GAIA) between 1985 and 2018. *Remote*
209 *Sensing of Environment* **236**, 111510 (2020).
- 210 8. Geofabrik GmbH. OpenStreetMap Data Extracts - Geofabrik Download Server.
211 <https://download.geofabrik.de/>.
- 212 9. Eurostat. Countries - GISCO archive. [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/countries)
213 [data/administrative-units-statistical-units/countries](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/countries).
- 214 10.UN. National Accounts - Analysis of Main Aggregates (AMA). *United Nations Statistics Division*
215 <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/snaama/> (2021).
- 216 11.World Bank Group. Population. *World Bank Data* <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL>
217 (2021).
- 218 12.World Bank Group. Urban Population Rate. *World Bank Data*
219 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.URB.TOTL.IN.ZS> (2021).
- 220 13.World Bank Group. Pump price for gasoline. *World Bank Data*
221 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EP.PMP.SGAS.CD> (2021).
- 222 14.World Bank Group. Renewable energy consumption. *World Bank Data*
223 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.FEC.RNEW.ZS> (2021).
- 224 15.IEA. Weather for Energy Tracker. *International Energy Agency* [https://www.iea.org/articles/weather-for-](https://www.iea.org/articles/weather-for-energy-tracker)
225 [energy-tracker](https://www.iea.org/articles/weather-for-energy-tracker) (2021).

- 226 16. Global Carbon Project. Supplementary data of Global Carbon Budget 2020 (Version 1.0) [Data set]. *Global*
227 *Carbon Project* <https://doi.org/10.18160/gcp-2020> (2020).
- 228 17. Friedlingstein, P. *et al.* Global Carbon Budget 2020. *Earth System Science Data* **12**, 3269–3340 (2020).
- 229 18. IEA. *World Energy Balances 2018*. <https://www.iea.org/statistics/balances/> (2018).
- 230 19. Riggio, J. *et al.* Global human influence maps reveal clear opportunities in conserving Earth’s remaining
231 intact terrestrial ecosystems. *Global Change Biology* **26**, 4344–4356 (2020).
- 232 20. Cohen, J., Cohen, P., West, G. & Aiken, L. S. *Applied Multiple Regression/Correlation Analysis for the*
233 *Behavioral Sciences*. (Erlbaum, 3rd edition, 2003).
- 234 21. Hastie, T. J., Tibshirani, R. J. & Wainwright, M. *Statistical Learning with Sparsity: The Lasso and*
235 *Generalizations*. (CRC Press, 2015).
- 236 22. Tibshirani, R. J. Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society,*
237 *Series B* **58**, 267–288 (1996).
- 238 23. Hoerl, A. & Kennard, R. Ridge Regression: Biased Estimation for Nonorthogonal Problems. *Technometrics*
239 **12**, 55–67 (1970).
- 240